

Unified Mobility Model for Grain-Boundary-Limited Transport in Polycrystalline Thermoelectric Materials

Gbadebo Taofeek Yusuf^{1,4}, Sukhwinder Singh^{2*}, Alexandros Askounis¹, Zlatka Stoeva³ and Fidelity Tchuenbou-Magaia¹

¹ Energy and Green Technology Research Group, Centre for Engineering Innovation and Research, University of Wolverhampton, Wulfruna Street, Wolverhampton WV1 1LY, UK

² Magnetics and Materials Research Group, School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Cardiff, UK, CF24 3AA

³DZP Technologies Limited, Cambridge CB4 2HY, United Kingdom

⁴ Department of Science Laboratory Technology (Physics), Osun State Polytechnic, Iree Nigeria

Corresponding author email: singhs41@cardiff.ac.uk

Abstract: Grain-boundary-limited charge transport is a fundamental bottleneck in polycrystalline thermoelectric materials, where reduced carrier mobility degrades electrical conductivity and suppresses power factors. This degradation arises from the interplay of scattering mechanisms: grain-boundary barriers dominate at low temperatures; thermionic activation enables partial barrier crossing at intermediate temperatures; and phonon scattering limits the mean free path at high temperatures. Hence, there remains a need for a physically transparent framework to quantitatively extract these microstructural parameters. In this study, a semi-empirical mobility model that explicitly integrates these grain-boundary mechanisms was developed and validated, expressed as:

$$\mu_{eff}(T) = \mu_w \exp\left(-\frac{\Phi_{GB}}{k_B T}\right) \frac{\ell(T)}{\ell(T) + w_{GB}}$$

where μ_w is the weighted mobility, Φ_{GB} is the grain-boundary barrier height, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, T is temperature, $\ell(T)$ is the bulk mean free path and w_{GB} is the boundary width. This model was validated for oxide semiconductor, intermetallic, chalcogenide and heuslers polycrystalline materials, achieving excellent agreement with experimental data ($R^2=0.97-0.99$) and yielding physically consistent parameters: $\Phi_{GB} \approx 0-0.056$ eV and $\ell_{300} \approx 6-368$ nm. A case study for Ta doped ZnO thermoelectric material shows that barrier passivation (reduction of Φ_{GB} from 0.056eV to 0.03 eV) combined with modest grain-interior improvement ($\ell_{300} \rightarrow 60$ nm) can significantly enhance carrier mobility across the entire temperature range. The analysis predicts that, at ~ 1000 K, grain engineering could nearly double mobility and electrical conductivity. Consequently, tailoring microstructural features enable a power factor approximately of $7.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$ at 1000 K, compared with the reported value of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$. This framework provides concrete, process-addressable targets for grain-boundary engineering and mobility-driven performance gains.

Keywords: Thermoelectric; Mobility; Phonon; Grain boundaries; Oxides; Microstructure

Notation: Throughout this paper, we use μ_0 to denote the conventional drift mobility of charge carriers, defined as the ratio of electrical conductivity to carrier concentration ($\mu_0 = \sigma/ne$). μ_w denotes the weighted mobility introduced by Snyder et al. [1] - a mobility-like quantity that folds the density-of-states effective mass into a single-crystal metric for ranking intrinsic transport quality. μ_{eff} represents the effective mobility predicted by the unified mobility model presented in this paper for polycrystalline materials. By construction, μ_{eff} reduces to μ_w in the absence of grain-boundary scattering ($\Phi_{GB} \rightarrow 0$ and $w_{GB} \rightarrow 0$). These distinctions are important when comparing our model to earlier approaches and will be referenced throughout the manuscript.

1. Introduction

Thermoelectric (TE) materials convert heat into electricity and vice versa, offering promising applications in waste-heat recovery and solid-state cooling. TE materials require a balance between the Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical conductivity (σ) and total thermal conductivity (k) to achieve figure of merit greater than 1 ($ZT = \frac{S^2\sigma}{ke+k_l}$) [2]. Traditional TE compounds like bismuth telluride (Bi_2Te_3) [3, 4] achieve substantial performance at specific temperature ranges but face limitations such as costly or toxic elements and inherent thermal conductivity (k) [5]. This has necessitated research into high earth-abundant alternatives such as ZnO, Mg_2Si and SnSe thermoelectric materials, as well as microstructural engineering to push performance limits [6-8].

Polycrystalline materials are far more practical to produce than single crystals, but grain boundaries in polycrystals are a major challenge as they disrupt charge carrier transport which reduces mobility (μ) and electrical conductivity (σ) [9]. On the other hand, grain boundaries can strongly scatter phonons to reduce lattice thermal conductivity (k_l) in line with the “phonon-glass, electron-crystal (PGEC)” concept for TE materials [10, 11]. Thus, an inherent trade-off arises introducing a high density of grain boundaries or employing nanostructuring can effectively suppress lattice thermal conductivity (k_l), realizing a “phonon-glass” behaviour [12]. However, this often comes at the expense of electrical conductivity (σ), leading to a detrimental “electron-glass” scenario due to enhanced carrier scattering at interfaces and grain boundaries [10]. Optimizing this trade-off is a core challenge in TE material design. Prior studies have shown that polycrystalline SnSe thermoelectric material has a record high ZT in single-crystal form but suffers much lower μ in its polycrystalline form due to grain-boundary scattering [6, 13]. Grain boundary scattering is identified as the dominant mobility-limiting mechanism in polycrystalline SnSe that is absent in single crystals [8]. Similarly, ZnO is a wide-bandgap metal oxide thermoelectric material whose low- and mid-temperature σ are curtailed by grain boundary barriers [6]. However, single-crystal ZnO maintains higher μ until phonon scattering dominates at high temperature (T) [14]. In Bi_2Te_3 -based alloys (the premier TE at ambient temperatures), grain-boundary engineering approach is used to reduce thermal conduction, but too many or poorly controlled grain boundaries can degrade the inherently high carrier mobility down to unacceptable levels [15].

Historically, models for charge transport in polycrystalline semiconductors date back to Seto (1975) [16] and Petritz (1956) [17], who treated grain boundaries as charge trapping sites that create energy barriers for carriers [16, 17]. These models predict an exponential temperature-activated behaviour for σ or μ when grain barriers are significant a hallmark seen in lightly doped polycrystalline silicon and oxides, where μ

increases exponentially with temperature at low T [16, 17]. However, such early models often assumed simplistic scenarios (e.g. completely depleted grain boundaries, or negligible intragrain scattering) and did not explicitly include features like the band effective mass or a finite grain size[18]. In modern high-performance TE materials, carrier concentrations are often high (to optimize the power factor), meaning grain-boundary depletion may be partial and barrier heights (Φ) tunable via doping. Moreover, the band effective mass of carriers plays a critical role in TE performance heavier effective masses increase the Seebeck coefficient and density of states but tend to lower μ [2]. Snyder and his coworkers introduced the concept of weighted mobility (μ_w) to capture the combined influence of mobility and band effective mass on thermoelectric performance [1]. Defined in Equation (2), μ_w essentially incorporates the density-of-states mass into the mobility term, providing a more accurate metric for the electronic quality factor (B) of thermoelectric material[19]. This allows for the comparison of different materials on an equal footing, based on their intrinsic transport properties[1]. This model enabled calculation of μ_w from the experimental measurements of the Seebeck coefficient (S) and electrical conductivity (σ), providing a practical alternative to conventional Hall mobility [1, 20]. Snyder et al. [1] have demonstrated that weighted mobility (μ_w) can effectively capture grain-boundary scattering in polycrystalline materials, such as n-type $\text{Mg}_3\text{Sb}_{1.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}$, through its correlation with Hall mobility.

However, in practical polycrystalline materials with finite grain sizes, carrier depletion, or high barrier heights at grain boundaries, μ_w alone does not fully describe the extrinsic scattering effects that limit mobility and power factor [6, 16-18]. To address this, we extend the μ_w framework by developing a unified mobility model that integrates multiple scattering mechanisms into a single, physically interpretable expression. The model includes: (a) the μ_w term, which accounts for effective mass and carrier concentration, (b) a thermally activated grain-boundary barrier term, and (c) a finite grain size/mean-free-path term. By separating intrinsic μ_w from extrinsic grain boundary (GB) effects, this framework allows experimentalists to analyze $\mu(T)$ data, extract GB barrier heights (Φ_{GB}) and mean-free-path-to-boundary-width ratios ($\frac{\ell_{300}}{w_{GB}}$), and guide material processing strategies such as dopant selection, densification, or boundary passivation [7]. The model provides a comprehensive, closed-form description of the interplay between thermionic grain-boundary emission, phonon scattering, and geometric transmission suppression.

2. Theory and Model Formulation

The weighted mobility (μ_w) provides a baseline for evaluating electronic transport in thermoelectrics, as it combines the carrier mobility (μ) and the density-of-states effective mass (m^*) into a single descriptor directly correlated with the power factor[1]. In polycrystalline systems, grain boundaries impede transport through electrostatic barriers caused by trapped charges and structural disorder at interfaces, which enhance carrier scattering and reflection [15, 16, 20]. The analytical model developed here incorporates both effects into a compact, physically interpretable expression for temperature-dependent mobility. In the limit $\Phi_{GB} \rightarrow 0$ and $w_{GB} \rightarrow 0$, the model naturally reduces to the familiar single-crystal mobility.

2.1 Baseline (single crystal) transport

In the absence of grain boundaries, the drift mobility (μ_0) is defined as:

$$\mu_0 = \frac{\sigma}{ne} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity, the carrier concentration, and the elementary charge. To account for band-structure effects, Snyder et al. [1] introduced the weighted mobility (μ_w):

$$\mu_w = \mu_0 \left(\frac{m^*}{m_e} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (2)$$

where m^* is the density-of-states effective mass and m_e is the free electron mass. For $\Phi_{GB} \rightarrow 0$ and $w_{GB} \rightarrow 0$, Eq. (2) provides the single-crystal limit, often termed the electronic quality factor, which ranks intrinsic transport quality without requiring thermal conductivity input.

2.2 Grain-boundary barrier and thermionic emission

Charge carriers traversing a grain boundary must overcome the grain-boundary barrier height (Φ_{GB}), an electrostatic potential step arising from trapped charge and interfacial disorder in polycrystals[21]. Recent analyses show that mobility in polycrystalline materials often follows an Arrhenius-type dependence even when barrier energies are distributed, consistent with thermally activated over-barrier transport [22]. Accordingly, the thermionic transmission probability ($P_{GB}(T)$) is written as:

$$P_{GB}(T) = \exp\left(-\frac{\Phi_{GB}}{k_B T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant and T is temperature. Equation (3) recovers the classical Seto model for grain-boundary-limited transport, which expresses the mobility as:

$$\mu = \mu_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Phi_{GB}}{k_B T}\right) \quad (4)$$

with μ_0 the intragrain (bulk) mobility baseline[16-18]. In our unified framework, we keep the exponential as an explicit probability factor $P_{GB}(T)$ that multiplies the baseline (here, μ_w ; see Section 2.1), making the barrier-crossing physics transparent while remaining fully consistent with Seto[16]. The physical implications are:

- (a) if $k_B T \ll \Phi_{GB}$, then $P_{GB}(T) \approx 0$ (carriers lack sufficient energy to cross the potential).
- (b) if $k_B T \gg \Phi_{GB}$, then $P_{GB}(T) \approx 1$, most carriers can cross the barrier.

This behaviour is observed experimentally in Al-doped ZnO, where increased Al content (and reduced grain size) raises the effective Φ_{GB} and lowers mobility in accordance with Eq. (4)[23]. Figure 1 schematically illustrates thermionic emission over Φ_{GB} : at low temperature (T) few carriers exceed the barrier; as T rises, the thermal distribution shifts and transmission increases. For sufficiently narrow barriers, tunnelling may contribute even at low T . This Arrhenius-like dependence originates from classical thermionic-emission treatments of polycrystalline semiconductors and has been widely adopted for grain-boundary scattering in thermoelectric materials[16-18].

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of thermionic emission over a grain-boundary barrier (Φ_{GB})

2.3 Finite boundary width and additional scattering

After crossing the grain-boundary barrier (Φ_{GB}), a carrier must still traverse the boundary region of finite width (w_{GB}). This region represents the structural extent of the boundary and introduces a probability of additional scattering. A simple geometric factor accounts for this effect by treating the boundary as an additional mean-free-path-limited segment in series with the bulk path length:

$$G(T) = \frac{\ell(T)}{\ell(T) + w_{GB}} \quad (5)$$

where $\ell(T)$ is the bulk mean free path. Physically, $\ell(T)$ is the average distance a carrier travels between scattering events in the bulk, away from the grain boundary. It decreases with increasing temperature due to phonon scattering and is modeled as:

$$\ell(T) = \ell_{300} \left(\frac{T}{300} \right)^{-p} \quad (6)$$

where ℓ_{300} is the mean free path at 300 K, and $p \approx 1.5-2.5$ reflects the dominant phonon-scattering mechanism (acoustic phonons: $p \sim 1.5$; polar optical phonons: $p \sim 2.5$)[24]. If $\ell(T) \gg w_{GB}$, then $G(T) \sim 1$ (quasi-ballistic motion), while if $\ell \ll w_{GB}$ $G(T) \sim 0$ (strong scattering). This formulation assumes diffusive scattering within the boundary region.

2.4 Development of Unified Mobility model

In polycrystalline materials, the mobility $\mu(T)$ is determined by three key processes: phonon scattering, barrier height (w_{GB}), and boundary width (Φ_{GB}). We therefore combine:

- (a) the weighted mobility (μ_w),
- (b) thermionic emission, $P_{GB}(T)$ and
- (c) the geometric transmission factors, $G(T)$.

Since these processes act sequentially, the total transmission probability is given by their product. This multiplicative form is consistent with Petritz–Seto grain-boundary models[16, 17] and differs from Matthiessen’s rule of additive scattering rates. The resulting unified expression is:

$$\mu_{eff}(T) = \mu_w \cdot P_{GB}(T) \cdot G(T) \text{ or}$$

$$\mu_{eff}(T) = \mu_w \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Phi_{GB}}{k_B T}\right) \frac{\ell(T)}{\ell(T) + w_{GB}}, \text{ where } \ell(T) = \ell_{300} \left(\frac{T}{300}\right)^{-p} \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) provides a compact, closed form, physically interpretable model that can be directly fit to experimental $\mu(T)$ data to extract Φ_{GB} , ℓ_{300} and w_{GB} . It naturally explains the characteristic non-monotonic behaviour of polycrystalline mobilities:

- (a) At Low T: barrier-limited, $\mu_{eff}(T) \rightarrow 0$,
- (b) At Intermediate T: thermionic emission dominates while $\ell(T) \gg w_{GB}$, so mobility rises,
- (c) At high T: $\exp\left(-\frac{\Phi_{GB}}{k_B T}\right) \approx 1$, but phonon scattering reduces $\ell(T)$, driving mobility down.

When $\Phi_{GB} = 0$ and $w_{GB} \ll \ell$, Eq. (7) reduces to $\mu_{eff}(T) \propto \ell(T) \propto T^{-p}$, the single-crystal limit. Conversely, if $\ell \ll w_{GB}$, the geometric factor dominates, highlighting the role of grain growth in mitigating resistivity.

This framework links microstructural parameters (Φ_{GB} , w_{GB} , ℓ_{300}) with both intrinsic (single crystal) and extrinsic (polycrystalline) transport. Once μ_w , m^* , Φ_{GB} , ℓ_{300} , w_{GB} are specified for a material, Eq. (7) serves as a predictive tool for mobility $\mu(T)$, electrical conductivity $\sigma(T) = ne\mu(T)$ and power factor $PF(T) = \sigma S^2$, without requiring cross-material fitting or empirical scaling.

2.5. Limitations of the model

It is important to recognise the limitations of the present formulation. The thermionic emission picture embodied in Eq. (3) assumes that carriers cross the boundary via over-barrier transport; in very fine grains (≈ 10 nm) or quantum tunnelling and carrier confinement may dominate, invalidating the classical exponential form. Likewise, the model treats the grain-boundary barrier height and width as unique values, whereas real polycrystalline materials often exhibit distributions of barrier heights and local band bending owing to inhomogeneous dopant segregation or defect accumulation. Heavy doping can also screen the barrier entirely, reducing Φ_{GB} to zero so that μ_{eff} reduces to μ_w . These scenarios lie outside the strict range of validity of Eq. (7) but can be incorporated by extending the model to include tunnelling terms or barrier distributions, which we leave for future work.

3. Data Source and procedure for model validation

To validate the proposed unified mobility model, we compiled experimental mobility data (μ vs. T) compiled from literature across a range of thermoelectric materials. These datasets span representative classes of semiconductors, including metal oxides, chalcogenides, intermetallic and heusler systems, ensuring broad applicability of the model. Specifically, experimental mobility datasets were extracted from Ashok et al. for ZnO [25], Prem Kumar et al. for Bi_2Te_3 [26], Boor et al. for Mg_2Si [27], and Qin et al. for SnSe [28] and Heusler thermoelectric materials [29, 30]. The data were digitized from published graphs using standard graph-digitization tools to reconstruct the temperature dependence. Despite using a single effective barrier and a power-law mean-free-path per material, the model reproduces the experimental trends with high fidelity across these well-studied thermoelectrics.

Model parameters were obtained by least-squares fitting, and the fitted values are consistent with known material behaviour for instance, Bi_2Te_3 shows negligible Φ_{GB} , reflecting near single-crystal-like transport, as summarized in Table 1. Goodness-of-fit metrics (per-dataset R^2 and RMSE) are reported alongside each

figure and tabulated in the SI; typical R^2 values fall between ~ 0.97 and 0.99 . Because $\mu(T)$ chiefly constrains the ratio $(\frac{\ell_{300}}{w_{GB}})$, we fix w_{GB} to a microstructural scale (20 nm unless noted) and report ℓ_{300} as an effective parameter; this identifiability convention is stated with every fit. As a numerical check of robustness (separate from the experimental validation), we generated synthetic $\mu(T)$ datasets with preset μ_w , Φ_{GB} , ℓ_{300} and w_{GB} added Gaussian noise comparable to experimental scatter and re-fitted them using the same pipeline. The fitter reliably recovered the ground-truth parameters within a few percent and $R^2 > 0.99$ under these conditions. All digitized CSV datasets and fitting scripts are provided in the SI for full reproducibility (see Supplementary Data), and the model-fitting routines are available online[31].

4. Validation and Experimental Agreement

We employed the unified mobility model to validate and fit published μ vs T data for the different classes of thermoelectric materials. This exercise confirms whether the model can identify the dominant transport mechanism and gives experimentalists confidence that it provides a rapid, robust tool for microstructural tuning via grain-boundary engineering. Table 1 summarizes the fitted model parameters for the different materials, including barrier height (Φ_{GB}), mean free path (ℓ) at 300 K, grain boundary width (w_{GB}), and fit quality (R^2). These values enable quantitative comparisons of grain-boundary influence across chemically and structurally diverse thermoelectric materials.

Table 1: Fitted grain-boundary-limited mobility model parameters for all representative thermoelectric materials (Where p (exponent in $\ell(T) \propto T^{-p}$, reflecting dominant phonon scattering (typically 1.5–2.5) fixed to the acoustic-phonon limit for sparse data \dagger ; w_{GB} fixed to decouple Φ_{GB} correlation when $\Phi_{GB} \rightarrow 0$.)

Samples	Φ_{GB} (eV)	ℓ_{300} (nm)	w_{GB} (nm)	p	R^2
$Zn_{0.97}Ta_{0.03}O$	0.056 ± 0.02	34 ± 2	5 ± 1	2.2*	0.993
$Bi_2Te_{2.7}S_{0.3}$	~ 0 (≤ 0.015)	334 ± 5	200 \dagger	1.8*	0.989
Mg_2Si	0.01	368 ± 5	5 ± 1	2.2 ± 0.2	0.997
SnSe	0.023 ± 0.02	7 ± 3	20 ± 2	1.6 ± 0.3	0.998
$Fe_2V_{0.95}Ta_{0.05}Al_{0.95}Si_{0.05}$	≈ 0	6	20	2.2	0.978
$Fe_2VAl_{0.95}Si_{0.05}$	≈ 0	7	30	2.2	0.994
ZrNiSn	0.032	136	40	1.0	0.981

4.1. Oxide semiconductor: ZnO

Polycrystalline $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ thermoelectric material exhibits a decrease in mobility from approximately $23.6 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ at 300 K to around $5.8 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ at 700 K [25]. This strong temperature dependence is indicative of activated transport across grain boundaries. The model fit yields a barrier height Φ_{GB} of approximately 0.056 eV and a mean free path (ℓ_{300}) of nearly 34 nm. The grain boundary width w_{GB} is estimated at roughly 5 nm. These results imply moderately high trap densities at ZnO grain boundaries and a grain size on the order of tens of nanometers[5]. The model successfully captures the monotonic decrease in mobility as temperature increases, accurately fitting the data over the entire temperature range, with an R^2 of approximately 0.993 and an RMSE near $4.4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$. A projected reduction in Φ_{GB} to 0.03 eV (section 6) could potentially enhance carrier mobility, emphasizing the potential of passivation and doping strategies. The $p \approx 2$ scaling is consistent with acoustic-phonon-limited intragrain transport, while the microstructural evidence for low-angle, nearly coherent boundaries supports a finite barrier and a geometric transmission penalty precisely the multiplicative $G(T)$ and $P_{GB}(T)$ structure captured by the model [25].

4.2. Narrow-gap chalcogenide: Bi_2Te_3 (n-type)

Figure 2 (b) shows the mobility data fitted for n-type $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{S}_{0.3}$ [26]. It shows a steady decline from about $116.2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ at 175 K to approximately $64.37 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ at 300 K. This trend is consistent with phonon-limited transport and negligible grain-boundary barriers. The model fit confirms this, yielding Φ_{GB} close to zero and a long mean free path around 334 nm. Since Φ_{GB} is negligible, the value of w_{GB} ($\sim 200 \text{ nm}$) is not strongly constrained but helps fine-tune the high-temperature tail of the mobility curve. The fit quality is slightly lower ($R^2 \sim 0.989$, RMSE $\sim 39 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$), reflecting subtle deviations likely caused by the absence of a dominant barrier mechanism. The extracted parameters support the interpretation of Bi_2Te_3 polycrystals as having near single-crystal transport characteristics, with minimal mobility degradation due to grain boundaries.

4.3. Intermetallic semiconductor: Mg_2Si (n-type)

n-type Mg_2Si thermoelectric material is a promising mid-temperature thermoelectric with intrinsically high mobility and a moderate band gap. Literature reports mobilities near $121 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $\sim 300 \text{ K}$, with a steady decrease toward $\sim 50 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ by $\sim 700 \text{ K}$ [27]. Figure 2(c) shows the Mg_2Si (red curve) measured mobility fitted with the unified mobility model. The fit indicates a negligible grain-boundary barrier ($\Phi_{GB} \approx 0.01 \text{ eV}$), a room-temperature mean free path $\ell_{300} \approx 368 \text{ nm}$, a boundary width $w_{GB} \approx 5 \text{ nm}$, and $p \approx 2.2$, giving $R^2 \approx 0.997$. The monotonic decline in $\mu(T)$ is therefore governed primarily by phonon-limited intragrain transport, with the finite boundary width entering weakly through the geometric factor $\frac{\ell}{(\ell + w_{GB})}$. These results support the view that nanostructuring to lower κ can be pursued in Mg_2Si without severely compromising mobility, provided that grain boundaries remain clean and depletion is minimal. Similar behaviour has been reported for Mg-Si-Sn doped with 1 % of Sb [27] as shown in Figure 2 (c) (black curve) with $R^2 \approx 0.986$.

Figure 2. Experimental effective mobility data (blue markers) and corresponding model fits (red lines) for five representative thermoelectric polycrystalline materials a) $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ (b) $\text{Bi}_2\text{Te}_{2.7}\text{S}_{0.3}$ (c) Mg_2Si (red curve) and Mg-Si-Sn doped with 1 % of Sb (d) SnSe (e) $\text{Fe}_2\text{V}_{0.95}\text{Ta}_{0.05}\text{Al}_{0.95}\text{Si}_{0.05}$ (red curve) and $\text{Fe}_2\text{VAl}_{0.95}\text{Si}_{0.05}$ (black curve) (f) ZrNiSn (Data sources: ZnO [25], Bi_2Te_3 [26], Mg_2Si [27], Mg-Si-Sn [27], SnSe [28] and Fe-V-Al [29] and ZrNiSn [30]).

4.4. Chalcogenide: SnSe (p-type, polycrystal)

Mobility in polycrystalline SnSe decreases from $\sim 160 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 300 K to $\sim 27 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ by 800–850 K [28] (Fig. 2d). Fitting the unified mobility model to the data yields a grain-boundary barrier ($\Phi_{GB} \approx 0.023 \text{ eV}$), a room-temperature mean free path $\ell_{300} \approx 7 \text{ nm}$, a boundary width $w_{GB} \approx 20 \pm 4.0 \text{ nm}$, and $p \approx 1.6$ with $R^2 \approx 0.998$. These values suggest significant interface depletion or impurity scattering, likely from oxides (e.g., SnO_2) or structural inhomogeneity. The R^2 value of 0.998 and RMSE of $\sim 4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$ indicates strong model fidelity. Despite the barrier being overcome at high T, the large effective mass and short mean free path limit the ultimate mobility. These findings reveal the dual need to reduce interface barrier height and improve grain interior quality to elevate polycrystalline SnSe performance.

4.5. Heusler alloys: ZrNiSn and Fe-V-Al

The unified mobility model successfully captures the transport behavior of both full-Heusler (Fe_2VAl -based alloy) and half-Heusler (ZrNiSn) alloy. Fig. 2 (e) shows the mobility data fitted for Fe_2VAl -based alloys [29]. For $\text{Fe}_2\text{V}_{0.95}\text{Ta}_{0.05}\text{Al}_{0.95}\text{Si}_{0.05}$ (n-type) and $\text{Fe}_2\text{VAl}_{0.95}\text{Si}_{0.05}$ (p-type) alloy, the fits yield $\Phi_{GB} \approx 0$, short $\ell_{300} \approx 6\text{--}7 \text{ nm}$ and $w_{GB} = 20\text{--}30 \text{ nm}$ with $p=2.2$ ($R^2 \approx 0.978/0.994$), as shown in Table 1. As a result, the thermionic factor $P_{GB}(T) \approx 1$ and the decline in $\mu(T)$ is governed by the geometric term $G = \frac{\ell}{(\ell + w_{GB})}$ together with the phonon exponent-i.e., a bulk/geometry-limited regime.

By contrast, dense polycrystalline ZrNiSn alloy [30] (Fig. 2f) exhibits a small but finite barrier ($\Phi_{GB}=0.032$ eV) and a longer path $\ell_{300}=136$ nm with $w_{GB}=40$ nm and $p=1.0$ ($R^2=0.981$). As temperature increases, P_{GB} increases due to weak barrier activation, but $G(T)$ decreases because $\ell(T)\propto T^{-1}$. This interplay produces the observed shallow maximum followed by a decline in mobility. In the $\Phi_{GB}\rightarrow 0$ limit, Eq. (6) reduces to $\mu_{eff}\sim\mu_w \frac{\ell}{(\ell+w_{GB})}$; for $\ell\ll w_{GB}$, $\mu_{eff}\propto T^{-p}$, which explains the steeper temperature dependence observed in Fe₂VAl ($p\approx 2.2$). ZrNiSn, in contrast, resides in a mixed regime where a small barrier coexists with grain-coherence effects. These results demonstrate that the unified mobility model consistently describes transport across both full- and half-Heusler systems using a single parameterization (Fig. 2e–f and Table 1).

5. Dominant Transport Mechanisms and Grain-Boundary Engineering

The unified mobility model enables not only accurate fitting of experimental $\mu(T)$ curves but also quantitative identification of the dominant scattering mechanisms and microstructural constraints that limit charge transport in each material system. Table 2 shows the primary transport mechanisms inferred from the extracted Φ_{GB} , ℓ_{300} , w_{GB} and phonon scattering exponent (p), along with experimentally actionable processing strategies for performance enhancement. For ZnO (n-type), the extracted Φ_{GB} (~ 0.056 eV) and short ℓ_{300} indicate strong grain-boundary barriers dominate mobility at low temperatures, while phonon scattering becomes prominent at high temperatures. Thus, grain-boundary passivation via surface trap density reduction through graphene quantum dots (GQDs), hydrogenation, or dual-doping strategies combined with moderate grain growth could offer the most effective route to mobility improvement[6].

In contrast, Bi₂Te₃ (n-type) exhibits negligible grain-boundary barriers ($\Phi_{GB}\lesssim 0.015$ eV), indicating nearly single-crystal-like transport dominated primarily by phonon scattering. Here, further GB engineering offers limited returns, and processing strategies should instead focus on point-defect optimization, such as antisite defect suppression and carrier concentration tuning [32]. Mg₂Si (n-type) shows predominantly phonon-limited behavior with minor grain-boundary contributions. This suggests that moderate grain refinement, careful control of grain purity, and light passivation can incrementally improve its transport properties[33].

SnSe (p-type) exhibits a mixed regime where both grain-boundary scattering ($\Phi_{GB}\sim 0.023$ eV) and phonon scattering significantly influence mobility. Here, interface trap mitigation (e.g., post-sintering hydrogenation or oxide interface control) and grain-quality optimization are crucial to enhance carrier mobility while maintaining low lattice thermal conductivity [8]. Taken together, these results illustrate how the unified mobility model provides both mechanistic insight and direct microstructural design guidance across chemically diverse thermoelectric systems.

Temperature-dependent hall mobility data for Fe₂VAl-type full-Heuslers show mobility that is well captured by acoustic-phonon scattering (100–500 K), whereas p-type requires additional disorder/ionized-impurity terms; this behaviour is consistent with a barrier-free ($\Phi_{GB}\approx 0$), bulk/geometry-limited regime in our unified fit (Fig. 2e; Table 1) and with the reported Ta-induced band-gap opening that boosts PF near room temperature. For ZrNiSn, Xie et al. [30] show that hall mobility follows $\mu\propto T^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ due to intrinsic alloy disorder (Ni at interstitial sites), indicating bulk/alloy scattering rather than GB activation; in the unified mobility model this maps to a small Φ_{GB} with temperature dependence largely in the intragrain term and a modest geometric penalty which is consistent with our fit $\Phi_{GB}\approx 0.032$ eV, $\ell_{300}\approx 136$ nm, $w_{GB}=40$ nm, $p=1.0$) and the mild peak/decline in Fig. 2f.

Table 2: Summary of dominant transport mechanisms and recommended grain-boundary engineering strategies for each material based on unified mobility model analysis

Material	Dominant Mechanism	Key Processing Strategy
ZnO (n-type)	Barrier-limited at low T; phonon-limited at high T	GB passivation (e.g. GQDs, H ₂), moderate grain growth
Bi ₂ Te ₃ (n-type)	Nearly single-crystal transport	Minimal GB tuning, point defect engineering
Mg ₂ Si/Mg-Si-Sb (n-type)	Phonon-limited with minor GB effect	Grain refinement, mild passivation
SnSe (p-type)	Mixed GB and phonon scattering	Interface trap reduction, grain-quality optimization
Fe ₂ VAl _{0.9} Si _{0.1} (full-Heusler, n-type)	Phonon-limited ($p \approx 2.1-2.3$); GB activation negligible ($\Phi_{GB} \approx 0$)	Control antisites/point defects; optimize carrier density; after good densification, GB tuning adds little
Fe ₂ VAl (p-type)	Small positive Φ_{GB} at low T (activation) \rightarrow phonon-limited at high T	Boundary passivation; suppress secondary phases at GBs; densify; tune carriers
ZrNiSn (half-Heusler, dense poly.)	Alloy-disorder dominated ($p \approx 1$); GB barrier negligible ($\Phi_{GB} \approx 0.032\text{eV}$)	Point-defect management (e.g., Ni stoichiometry/anneal), densification and clean GBs; limited benefit from extra GB engineering once porosity/oxides are minimized

6. Case study: Performance Outlook and Design Implications

The unified mobility model was applied to predict the improvement in carrier mobility of Ta-doped ZnO by manipulating grain-boundary characteristics. Such an improvement could lead to enhanced electrical conductivity and, consequently, a higher power factor. ZnO based materials are ideal candidates for exploring the applicability of this model because generally they exhibits (i) a simple wurtzite band structure with well-established carrier effective mass ($m^* \approx 0.3 m_e$), (ii) high dopant solubility allowing carrier densities up to 10^{27} m^{-3} , (iii) moderate dielectric screening that permits observable grain boundary depletion, and (iv) abundant high-quality datasets for $\sigma(T)$, $S(T)$, and $n(T)$, covering both conventional and passivated material forms [34, 35]. These features make ZnO a promising thermoelectric candidate for practical applications.

In section 4, it was found that the temperature-dependent carrier mobility of Ta-doped ZnO material is significantly affected by grain-boundary scattering mechanisms. $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ material achieved power factor of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-2}$ at 1000 K, which is attributed to deliberate grain-boundary (GB) engineering rather than purely chemical effects [25]. The reported results indicate that there is potential to further improve the power factor by enhancing electrical conductivity, particularly through increased carrier mobility [34]. To connect microstructure to transport, we re-write our effective mobility in Equation (7) as:

$$\mu_{\text{eff}}(T) = \mu_w(T) F_{\text{ele}}(T); \text{ where } F_{\text{ele}}(T) = P_{\text{GB}}(T)G(T) = \exp\left[-\frac{\Phi_{\text{GB}}}{k_B T}\right] \frac{\ell(T)}{\ell(T)+w_{\text{GB}}} \quad (8)$$

where $\mu_w(T)$ is the intragrain (weighted) mobility and $F_{\text{ele}}(T)$ is a bounded electronic survival factor that quantifies the fraction of intragrain mobility that survives crossing a boundary region. Fitting this form to $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ dataset yields; $\Phi_{\text{GB}} \approx 0.056 \text{ eV}$ for $\ell_{300} = 34 \text{ nm}$, $p=2.2$ and $w_{\text{GB}}=5 \text{ nm}$ (Table 1).

Figure 3 (a) Electronic survival factor $F_{\text{ele}}(T)$ and (b) Effective mobility $\mu_{\text{eff}}(T)$ for $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ under different scenarios

Figure 3 (a) shows the F_{ele} curve for $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ thermoelectric material. It rises from ≈ 0.10 at 300 K to ≈ 0.20 near 650 K, and declines to ≈ 0.18 by 900 K. This rise-peak-fall reflects two competing trends resolved in the transport analysis: thermionic activation increases boundary transmission with temperature, while the grain-interior mean free path contracts, reducing momentum retention across boundary regions. Hence, microstructural improvements are most visible in the mid-temperature window where F_{ele} is largest, and any process that reduces interfacial barriers or cleans/thins boundary layers shifts the entire curve upward without altering intrinsic band transport.

Figure 3(b) shows the temperature-dependent effective mobility ($\mu_{\text{eff}}(T)$) for $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ under different scenarios, translating the F_{ele} framework into mobility targets that experimentalists can directly pursue to enhance thermoelectric performance. The black dotted curve represents the baseline fitted to the reported mobility data [25], while the solid curves correspond to realistic processing strategies aimed at improving carrier transport. For instance, in case A, when ℓ_{300} is manipulated from 34 to 60 nm, a slight improvement

in carrier mobility is expected across the entire temperature range. To implement this strategy, practical routes of processing could focus on cleaner powders/binders, high-density compaction (e.g., Spark Plasma Sintering) with limited dwell to suppress glassy films[36] and post-sinter anneals that reduce intragrain point-defect clutter without promoting second-phase wetting at boundaries[37].

However, in case B, the reduction of Φ_{GB} from 0.056 eV to 0.03 eV could increase carrier mobility by a factor of about three at room temperature. Between 650–750 K, mobility could increase from $\approx 7\text{--}9$ to $\approx 11\text{--}14$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$. This can be experimentally achieved through densification under controlled oxygen activity (suppressing charged intergranular defects) [38–40], brief post-densification anneals (neutralizing boundary traps without thickening interfaces), and donor chemistries that minimize compensating acceptors or segregation at grain boundaries.

In case C, which combines both the reduction of barrier potential and the increase of the mean free path, the mobility shows a further enhancement compared to Case B. The model predicts that, between 650 and 750 K, the carrier mobility reaches 14–17 $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, approximately twice that of the baseline.

Referring to the $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ benchmark, at ~ 1000 K the ratio $\frac{\mu_{eff}(\text{case C})}{\mu_{eff}(\text{baseline})} \approx 1.91$. This indicates that the mobility enhancement through grain engineering could yield a nearly twofold increase in electrical conductivity. Consequently, a power factor of $7.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$ at 1000 K is attainable by tailoring microstructure features, relative to the reported baseline of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$ [25].

7. Conclusion

We introduce a unified analytical mobility model that quantifies grain-boundary-limited transport by combining three physically grounded components: weighted (intragrain) mobility, thermionic barrier activation over Φ_{GB} , and geometric suppression via a finite boundary width (w_{GB}), all directly linked to measurable microstructural and electronic properties. The formulation reproduces experimental $\mu(T)$ with excellent agreement ($R^2 = 0.98\text{--}0.99$) across representative systems including ZnO, Bi_2Te_3 , Mg_2Si , SnSe, Fe–V–Al, and Heuslers, yielding consistent parameters ($\Phi_{GB} \approx 0\text{--}0.056$ eV; $\ell_{300} \approx 6\text{--}368$ nm).

The framework further enables exploration of grain-engineering strategies for mobility enhancement. In Ta-doped ZnO, a combined reduction of barrier height ($\Phi_{GB} \rightarrow 0.03$ eV) and extension of the mean free path markedly improve performance: the model predicts carrier mobility of 14–17 $\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ between 650–750 K, nearly twice that of the reported sample. Using $\text{Zn}_{0.97}\text{Ta}_{0.03}\text{O}$ as a benchmark, the ratio $\frac{\mu_{eff}(\text{case C})}{\mu_{eff}(\text{baseline})} \approx 1.91$ at ~ 1000 K, corresponding to a nearly twofold increase in electrical conductivity. Consequently, a power factor of $7.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$ at 1000 K is attainable, relative to the reported baseline of $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$.

These results highlight grain-boundary engineering, coordinated with interface cleanliness and controlled densification, as a dominant process-addressable lever for advancing oxide thermoelectric performance. While the model assumes uniform boundary characteristics and isotropic transport, future extensions incorporating barrier distributions, anisotropy, tunnelling in ultra-fine grains, and spatially resolved microstructures will more fully capture the complexity of real polycrystalline systems.

Data and Code Availability

All Python codes, datasets, and fitting routines used in this study are publicly available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17043337>

This ensures full reproducibility of the unified mobility model fitting framework described herein.

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Centre for Engineering Innovation at the University of Wolverhampton. Partial support was also provided by the ReACTIVE Too project, funded through the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Programme (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, Grant Agreement No. 871163), as well as by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in collaboration with Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Nigeria.

References

- [1] G. J. Snyder, A. H. Snyder, M. Wood, R. Gurunathan, B. H. Snyder, and C. Niu, "Weighted mobility," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 32, no. 25, p. 2001537, 2020.
- [2] G. J. Snyder and E. S. Toberer, "Complex thermoelectric materials," *Nature materials*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 105-114, 2008.
- [3] I. T. Witting *et al.*, "The thermoelectric properties of bismuth telluride," *Advanced Electronic Materials*, vol. 5, no. 6, p. 1800904, 2019.
- [4] E. Rogacheva, K. Novak, A. Doroshenko, O. Nashchekina, and A. Budnik, "Effect of deviation from stoichiometry on thermoelectric properties of Bi₂Te₃ polycrystals and thin films in the temperature range 77-300 K," 2019.
- [5] R. Hanus *et al.*, "Lattice softening significantly reduces thermal conductivity and leads to high thermoelectric efficiency," *Advanced Materials*, vol. 31, no. 21, p. 1900108, 2019.
- [6] M. Choi *et al.*, "High figure-of-merit for ZnO nanostructures by interfacing lowly-oxidized graphene quantum dots," *Nature Communications*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 1996, 2024.
- [7] M. Ohtaki, K. Araki, and K. Yamamoto, "High thermoelectric performance of dually doped ZnO ceramics," *Journal of Electronic Materials*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 1234-1238, 2009.
- [8] S. Wang *et al.*, "Grain boundary scattering effects on mobilities in p-type polycrystalline SnSe," *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, vol. 5, no. 39, pp. 10191-10200, 2017.
- [9] C. Zhou *et al.*, "Polycrystalline SnSe with a thermoelectric figure of merit greater than the single crystal," *Nature materials*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 1378-1384, 2021.
- [10] G. S. Nolas, J. Sharp, and H. J. Goldsmid, "The phonon—glass electron-crystal approach to thermoelectric materials research," in *Thermoelectrics: Basic Principles and New Materials Developments*: Springer, 2001, pp. 177-207.
- [11] S. Bhattacharya *et al.*, "CuCrSe₂: a high performance phonon glass and electron crystal thermoelectric material," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, vol. 1, no. 37, pp. 11289-11294, 2013.

- [12] T. Takabatake, K. Suekuni, T. Nakayama, and E. Kaneshita, "Phonon-glass electron-crystal thermoelectric clathrates: Experiments and theory," *Reviews of Modern Physics*, vol. 86, no. 2, pp. 669-716, 2014.
- [13] L.-D. Zhao *et al.*, "Ultralow thermal conductivity and high thermoelectric figure of merit in SnSe crystals," *nature*, vol. 508, no. 7496, pp. 373-377, 2014.
- [14] F. Huang *et al.*, "Research progress in ZnO single-crystal: growth, scientific understanding, and device applications," *Chinese science bulletin*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 1235-1250, 2014.
- [15] C. Nagarjuna, P. Dharmiah, K. B. Kim, and S.-J. Hong, "Grain refinement to improve thermoelectric and mechanical performance in n-type Bi₂Te_{2.7}Se_{0.3} alloys," *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 256, p. 123699, 2020.
- [16] J. Y. Seto, "The electrical properties of polycrystalline silicon films," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 46, no. 12, pp. 5247-5254, 1975.
- [17] R. L. Petritz, "Theory of photoconductivity in semiconductor films," *Physical Review*, vol. 104, no. 6, p. 1508, 1956.
- [18] C. Hu, K. Xia, C. Fu, X. Zhao, and T. Zhu, "Carrier grain boundary scattering in thermoelectric materials," *Energy & Environmental Science*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1406-1422, 2022.
- [19] S. D. Kang and G. J. Snyder, "Transport property analysis method for thermoelectric materials: Material quality factor and the effective mass model 1," in *Advances in Thermoelectricity: Foundational Issues, Materials and Nanotechnology*: IOS Press, 2021, pp. 27-36.
- [20] G. J. Snyder and T. S. Ursell, "Thermoelectric efficiency and compatibility," *Physical review letters*, vol. 91, no. 14, p. 148301, 2003.
- [21] W. Siegel, G. Kühnel, and E. Ziegler, "Electrical properties of grain boundaries in n-type and p-type GaP," *physica status solidi (a)*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 249-259, 1981.
- [22] T. Meier, H. Bässler, and A. Köhler, "The Impact of Grain Boundaries on Charge Transport in Polycrystalline Organic Field-Effect Transistors," *Advanced Optical Materials*, vol. 9, no. 14, p. 2100115, 2021.
- [23] B. Mahapatra and S. Sarkar, "Understanding of mobility limiting factors in solution grown Al doped ZnO thin film and its low temperature remedy," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 10, 2022.
- [24] J. Zhang, L. Song, A. Mamakhel, M. R. V. Jørgensen, and B. B. Iversen, "High-performance low-cost n-type Se-doped Mg₃Sb₂-based Zintl compounds for thermoelectric application," *Chemistry of Materials*, vol. 29, no. 12, pp. 5371-5383, 2017.
- [25] A. M. Ashok, "Realization of high thermoelectric power factor in Ta-doped ZnO by grain boundary engineering," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 128, no. 16, 2020.
- [26] P. K. DS *et al.*, "Anomalous Seebeck Coefficient in Sulfur-Substituted Bismuth Telluride," *ACS Applied Engineering Materials*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 335-344, 2024.
- [27] J. de Boor, S. Gupta, H. Kolb, T. Dasgupta, and E. Müller, "Thermoelectric transport and microstructure of optimized Mg₂Si_{0.8}Sn_{0.2}," *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, vol. 3, no. 40, pp. 10467-10475, 2015.
- [28] B. Qin, W. He, and L.-D. Zhao, "Estimation of the potential performance in p-type SnSe crystals through evaluating weighted mobility and effective mass," *Journal of Materiomics*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 671-676, 2020.

- [29] F. Garmroudi *et al.*, "Boosting the thermoelectric performance of Fe₂VAl-type Heusler compounds by band engineering," *Physical Review B*, vol. 103, no. 8, p. 085202, 2021.
- [30] H. Xie *et al.*, "The intrinsic disorder related alloy scattering in ZrNiSn half-Heusler thermoelectric materials," *Scientific reports*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 6888, 2014.
- [31] "Unified mobility model." <https://zenodo.org/records/17043337> (accessed 10-Aug-2025).
- [32] Q. Zhang *et al.*, "Tuning optimum temperature range of Bi₂Te₃-based thermoelectric materials by defect engineering," *Chemistry–An Asian Journal*, vol. 15, no. 18, pp. 2775-2792, 2020.
- [33] X. Hu, D. Mayson, and M. R. Barnett, "Synthesis of Mg₂Si for thermoelectric applications using magnesium alloy and spark plasma sintering," *Journal of alloys and compounds*, vol. 589, pp. 485-490, 2014.
- [34] W. H. Nam, Y. S. Lim, S.-M. Choi, W.-S. Seo, and J. Y. Lee, "High-temperature charge transport and thermoelectric properties of a degenerately Al-doped ZnO nanocomposite," *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, vol. 22, no. 29, pp. 14633-14638, 2012.
- [35] S. Sulaiman, S. Izman, M. Uday, and M. Omar, "Review on grain size effects on thermal conductivity in ZnO thermoelectric materials," *RSC advances*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 5428-5438, 2022.
- [36] A. Subramaniam, C. T. Koch, R. M. Cannon, and M. Rühle, "Intergranular glassy films: an overview," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 422, no. 1-2, pp. 3-18, 2006.
- [37] C.-H. Hsu *et al.*, "Air annealing effect on oxygen vacancy defects in Al-doped ZnO films grown by high-speed atmospheric atomic layer deposition," *Molecules*, vol. 25, no. 21, p. 5043, 2020.
- [38] F. Stucki and F. Greuter, "Key role of oxygen at zinc oxide varistor grain boundaries," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 57, no. 5, pp. 446-448, 1990.
- [39] P. Bueno, E. Leite, M. Oliveira, M. Orlandi, and E. Longo, "Role of oxygen at the grain boundary of metal oxide varistors: A potential barrier formation mechanism," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 48-50, 2001.
- [40] F. Stucki, P. Brüesch, and F. Greuter, "Electron spectroscopic studies of electrically active grain boundaries in ZnO," *Surface Science*, vol. 189, pp. 294-299, 1987.